

Original Research

Modelling and Mapping of Soil Salinity Related to Soil Characteristics and Irrigation in a Semi-Arid Context

Yassine Al Masmoudi^{1*}, Sanae Bel-Lahbib¹, Khalid Ibno Namr¹, Adil Jouamaa², Meryem Moustakim³, Malika Laghrour⁴, Badr Rerhou⁵

Abstract

Soil salinity is a key challenge to maintaining agricultural operations in regions primarily defined by a semi-arid environment. Irrigation techniques are used to mitigate the impact of insufficient precipitation. However, excessive use of irrigation water creates significant problems of soil salinity. Utilising advanced methodologies, this investigation is dedicated to making models and maps of soil salinity. The approach involves the computation of the Normalised Differential Salinity Index (NDSI) while systematically examining potential correlations among the various physicochemical parameters under scrutiny: Soil Organic Matter (SOM), Electrical Conductivity (EC), pH, Texture, total limestone (CaCO₃) and Evapotranspiration (ET_o), in order to determine the parameters controlling salinity. The results showed a predominance of the sand fraction (57.5%), EC varied from 0.90 to 1.32 dS.m⁻¹, and exhibited varying salinity levels. Additionally, within the climate conditions of the region, climate analysis unveiled a noteworthy evapotranspiration rate (ET_o) ranging between 4 and 9 mm.day⁻¹. The model developed showed an adequate result in estimating soil salinity with an R²=0.90. Moreover, the map generated using NDSI showed that 36% of the total area displayed no evidence of salinity impact, 23% showed mild salinity, 24% indicated moderate soil salinity, and 17% showcased extreme levels of soil salinity. The proactive cartography of soil salinity in dry and semi-dry areas, coupled with an advanced modelling technique employing remote sensing data, stands as an integral methodology for informed decision-making processes.

Keywords

Irrigation, Soil salinity prediction, Modelling and Mapping, Electrical Conductivity, NDSI, Semi-arid conditions

1 Laboratory of Geosciences and Environmental Techniques, Department of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Chouaib Doukkali University, BP.20, 24000 El Jadida, Morocco

2 Industrial and Seismic Engineering Research Team, Mohammed First University National School of Applied Sciences of Oujda, 60000, Morocco

3 Unit of Irrigation and Climate Change, Division of Water and Climate, National Centre for Energy, Sciences and Nuclear Techniques, Rabat, Morocco

4 International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas, Avenue Hafiane Cherkaoui, Rabat 10112, Morocco

5 Department of Natural Resources and Environment, Hassan II Institute of Agronomy and Veterinary Medicine, PO Box 6202, Madinat Al Irfane 10101, Rabat, Morocco

* Corresponding author:

E-mail address: yassine.almasmoudi@gmail.com

Citation: Al Masmoudi, Y., Bel-Lahbib, S., Ibno Namr, K., Jouamaa, A., Moustakim, M., Laghrour, M., Rerhou, B. (2026). Modelling and Mapping of Soil Salinity Related to Soil Characteristics and Irrigation in a Semi-Arid Context. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (2)

Received: 09.08.2025 / **Accepted:** 05.02.2026 /

Published: 24.02.2026

<http://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.2.23520>

This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY SA) license

Modeliranje in kartiranje slanosti tal v povezavi z značilnostmi tal in namakanjem v polsušnem okolju

Izvleček

Slanost tal je ključni izziv za ohranjanje kmetijske dejavnosti v regijah, ki jih v glavnem zaznamuje polsušno okolje. Za ublažitev vpliva nezadostnih padavin se uporabljajo namakalne tehnike, a prekomerna uporaba namakalne vode povzroča znatne probleme s slanostjo tal. Naša raziskava je namenjena izdelavi modelov in zemljevidov slanosti tal s pomočjo naprednih tehnologij. Pristop vključuje izračun normaliziranega diferencialnega indeksa slanosti (NDSI) ob sistematičnem preučevanju potencialnih korelacij med različnimi fizikalno-kemijskimi parametri: organska snov v tleh (SOM), električna prevodnost (EC), pH, tekstura, skupni apnenec (CaCO_3) in evapotranspiracija (ET_0), da se določijo parametri, ki uravnavajo slanost. Rezultati so pokazali prevlado frakcije peska (57,5 %), EC je nihal od 0,90 do 1,32 $\text{dS}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ in pokazal različne ravni slanosti. Poleg tega je analiza podnebja v podnebnih razmerah regije razkrila opazno stopnjo evapotranspiracije (ET_0) med 4 in 9 $\text{mm}\cdot\text{dan}^{-1}$. Razvit model je pokazal ustrezen rezultat pri ocenjevanju slanosti tal z $R^2=0,90$. Poleg tega je zemljevid, ustvarjen z uporabo NDSI, pokazal, da 36 % celotne površine ni kazalo znakov vpliva slanosti, 23 % je kazalo blago slanost, 24 % je kazalo zmerno slanost tal, 17 % pa je kazalo ekstremne ravni slanosti tal. Proaktivna kartografija slanosti tal v suhih in polsuhih območjih, skupaj z napredno tehniko modeliranja, ki uporablja podatke daljinskega zaznavanja, predstavlja celovito metodologijo za informirane procese odločanja.

Ključne besede

Namakanje, napovedovanje slanosti tal, modeliranje in kartiranje, električna prevodnost, NDSI, polsušne razmere

Introduction

Environmental stresses, notably soil salinity, have significantly impacted the sustainability of soil and the cultivation of agricultural crops (Shrivastava and Kumar, 2015). The increase of salinity in soil and water was noted at the beginning of the 21st century (Yamaguchi and Blumwald, 2005). Regarded as one of the most destructive environmental stressors, soil salinity has precipitated critical reductions in agricultural areas (Yamaguchi and Blumwald, 2005; Shahbaz and Ashraf, 2013). Approximately 10 hectares of agricultural land are lost every minute globally, with salinisation contributing to 30% of this overall loss (FAO, 2020). In Mediterranean soils, the accumulation of salt is mostly a natural process that is made easier by the area's ecological characteristics (Aragüés and Tanji, 2003). This happens a lot in Africa, which has 63% of the world's salty soils (Kahime et al, 2018). Specifically, in semi-arid areas, intense use of water resources causes a lot of evaporation, which makes soils and groundwater salty (Khan et al, 2016; Jamaa et al, 2020). Drainage and evapotrans-

piration are important factors in fostering this process, especially in semi-arid and arid areas. Additionally, the ascent of water from shallow salty aquifers contributes to soil salinisation (FAO, 2020). Crops can absorb important nutrients from the soluble salts formed in irrigated soils. However, successive irrigations with saline water prompt the salts in the soil to expand. Consequently, a study on sugar beet crops by Rerhou et al (2023) in the Doukkala plain of Morocco demonstrates that, at high rates, this accumulation would affect root development and plant growth. This accelerates land degradation in semi-arid Mediterranean environments, especially in agricultural regions using poor-quality water for irrigation systems (Rahoui et al., 2000; El Achheb et al., 2001; Aragüés and Tanji, 2003). In essence, the expansion of salinized areas can be attributed to various factors, including soil-related elements (such as permeability, water depth, groundwater quality and topography), climatic conditions (like low rainfall and humidity), elevated surface evaporation, proximity to the sea, and management factors (involving irrigation, drainage, and cultural practices) (Ug and

Douaik, 2008; Ben-Dor et al., 2009). The mobility of water and air in the soil, the capacity of plants to hold water and root penetration are all affected by salt in the soil. In different studies (Curtis and Lauchli, 1986; Suárez and Medina, 2005; Al-Maskri et al., 2010; Amirul et al., 2014; Ors and Suarez, 2017), under salinity stress, a decrease in plant biomass, leaf area, and growth has been noted in a variety of vegetable crops. These salts can also impede the development of plants (Tang et al., 2015; Yadav et al., 2020). Salinity stress impacts various stages of plant growth, including seed germination, which is recognised as the stage that is most susceptible and crucial to abiotic stress (Patade et al., 2011). In addition to the environmental and agronomic impacts, soil salinity has socio-economic impacts (Sidike et al., 2014), mainly in arid and semi-arid zones (FAO, 2002; Farifteh et al., 2006; Allbed et al., 2014; El Harti et al., 2016). The FAO estimates that there are around 27.3 million hectares of areas affected by salt in the Mediterranean basin, including Morocco. Being an arid and semi-arid country, Morocco remains concerned about the ongoing degradation of soil due to salinisation, and the number of regions in Morocco affected by this phenomenon is increasing with a low rainfall rate (Oumara and El Youssefi, 2022). The second biggest threat to crop production is salinisation (Montanarella et al., 2016), after erosion, which is also considered a serious threat (Moustakim et al., 2019; 2022), and soil compaction (Al Masmoudi et al., 2019; 2021). This negatively affects the country, as the agriculture sector contributes significantly to Morocco's economic development (Oumara and El Youssefi, 2022). Conventionally, the evaluation of soil salinity traditionally involves collecting on-site soil samples, followed by laboratory analysis to measure electrical conductivity. However, these techniques are resource-intensive and economically challenging due to the need for extensive sampling to accurately capture the spatial variations within a given region (Nanni and Dematté, 2006; Brunner et al., 2007). Remote sensing has surpassed traditional methods in evaluating salinity, providing more comprehensive and efficient rapid evaluation techniques to manage and map the salinity in the soil in a professional manner (Allbed and Kumar, 2013). Several studies have adopted remote sensing and GIS-related approaches to effectively and efficiently study, map, and model the spatial and temporal variability of soil salinity across different environmental contexts (Rao and Kumar, 1991; Srivastava et al., 1997; Eldeiry and Garcia, 2008, 2010; Jiapaer et

al., 2011). Once it involves mapping soil salinity, remote sensing has many scientific advantages over traditional field-based methods (Ben-Dor et al., 2008; Bai et al., 2016; Bannari, 2019). Remote sensing data and methodologies are better and less costly tools for rapidly verifying and visualising soil salinity (Allbed and Kumar, 2013). Several remote sensing indices, like the salinity index (SI), the normalised difference salinity index (NDSI), the brightness index (BI), and the normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), were used to see how well they worked at mapping soil salinity in dry areas (Douaoui et al., 2006; Jiapaer et al., 2011). Recent advances in remote sensing have significantly improved soil salinity assessment in arid and semi-arid regions. Satellite imagery allows the identification of salinity patterns over large areas and helps to better capture their spatial variability. When combined with field measurements, remote sensing provides an effective alternative to traditional field-based methods. In the Doukkala region of Morocco, agriculture stands as the primary activity for the local population. The arid climate, proximity to the sea, marine intrusion, and the declining quality of irrigation water collectively contribute to the deterioration of agricultural soils (Bel-Lahbib et al., 2022; El Bourhrami et al., 2022; Bounif et al., 2023). Despite the vital role of agriculture, there have been limited studies on the quantification, sources, and spatial variability of soil salinity in Morocco. Comprehensive data regarding soil salinity across various regions of the country are scarce. Since there hasn't been any modelling done on soil salinity in the research region, this study is crucial for managing and forecasting soil salinity; its goal is to assess the degree of salinity using both remote sensing data and on-site observation/evaluation.

This study aims to model and map soil salinity in the Doukkala region of Morocco and to support decision-making through a comprehensive strategy combining scientific and policy-oriented interventions. The originality of the work lies in its integrated approach, which combines field soil analyses, climatic data derived from the Penman–Monteith model, and satellite-based salinity indices to develop a robust framework for soil salinity mapping in semi-arid agricultural environments. Although the Doukkala region was selected as a case study, the proposed methodology is transferable to other arid and semi-arid regions facing similar salinisation issues. The main objectives are to analyse the spatial distribution of soil salinity and to support sustainable soil and irrigation management.

Materials and Methods

Study area description and climatic conditions

This study was done in the Doukkala plain, located in Central Morocco (Fig. 1). The Doukkala region forms a segment of the expansive western Moroccan Meseta. Geomorphologically, it comprises three distinct units: the coastal edge, the Sahel, and the plain (Eljebri et al., 2019). The Doukkala Abda area has semi-arid winters and hot, dry summers that are affected by the maritime environment. The temperature fluctuates between 5 and 39 °C. October through May is the rainy period, with an average yearly rainfall of roughly 317 mm (Ait Ayad et al., 2023). The National Meteorological Service of Morocco, which is in charge of data collection and quality control, gathered the climatic dataset from thirty local weather stations, and the computation of evapotranspiration employed the Penman-Monteith model. Figure 2 presents the ombrothermic diagram during the 2019 crop year.

Soil sampling and analysis

During 2019, 500 soil samples (0-30 cm) were collected from diverse locations across the study area. Soil samples were collected during the 2019 agricultural campaign, mainly between March and May, before the period of intensive irrigation and crop maturation. The analyses comprised a comprehensive assessment of soil properties, including soil organic matter (SOM) utilising the Walkley and Black method (1934), CaCO₃ measured with the Bernard calcimeter, soil texture determined through the Robinson method (Robinson et al, 1997), and the evaluation of water pH and electrical conductivity (EC). Figure 1 provides an overview of soil sampling and the distinct meteorological stations utilised for data analysis in this study.

The soil classifications in the research area, used to determine soil salinity, are based on the agronomic classification of soil salinity, as shown in Table 1. This comprehensive classification system allows for a nuanced evaluation of the diverse salt-affected zones present, providing a strong framework for studying the differences in salinity levels across different soil types within the study region.

Figure 1. Geographic location of the Doukkala irrigated perimeter, meteorological stations, and soil sampling.

Slika 1. Geografska lokacija namakalne površine Doukkala, meteoroloških postaj in vzorčenja tal.

Figure 2. Climatic conditions (Precipitation [mm] and Temperature [°C]) in the Doukkala region: 57-year average and the 2019 agricultural campaign.

Slika 2. Podnebne razmere (padavine [mm] in temperatura [°C]) v regiji Doukkala: 57-letno povprečje in kmetijska kampanja 2019.

Tabela 1. Agronomic classification of soil salinity based on EC (Brown et al, 1954).

Table 1. Agronomska klasifikacija slanosti tal na podlagi EC (Brown et al, 1954).

Classification	EC dS.m-1	Crop yield
Non-saline soils	0-2	Not affected
Slightly saline soils	2-4	Sensitive crops affected
Saline soils	4-8	Many crops affected
Strongly saline soils	8-16	Only tolerant crops are possible
Extremely saline soils	>16	Few very tolerant crops are possible

Estimation of reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) based on the FAO Penman–Monteith equation

The reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) was calculated using the FAO Penman-Monteith equation (Eq. 1), with daily meteorological information obtained from 30 meteorological stations established in the study area. Daily meteorological records required to compute ET_0 (Allen et al., 1998), including air temperature, solar radiation, humidity, wind speed and rainfall, were collected by these stations. Daily ET_0 values at each station were estimated by the FAO Penman-Monteith equation. These values were averaged

across the soil sample period to describe the mean evapotranspiration environment during the study period. Spatial distribution of the mean ET_0 in the study region.

$$ET_0 = \frac{0.408\Delta(Rn-G) + \gamma \frac{900}{(T+273)} U_2 (e_s - e_a)}{\Delta + \gamma(1+0.34U_2)} \quad (1)$$

Where Rn is the net radiation at the crop surface ($MJ\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$), G the soil heat flux density ($MJ\ m^{-2}\ day^{-1}$), T the air temperature at 2 m height ($^{\circ}C$), u_2 the wind speed at 2 m height ($m\ s^{-1}$), e_s the vapour pressure of the air at saturation (kPa), e_a the actual vapour pressure (kPa), D the slope of the vapour pressure curve ($kPa\ ^{\circ}C^{-1}$) and g is the psychrometric constant ($kPa\ ^{\circ}C^{-1}$).

Mapping of soil salinity using GIS and remote sensing

Table 2 details some of the indices reported in the literature to map soil salinity in the current study. In addition, the Normalised Differential Salinity Index (NDSI) was obtained from one Landsat 8 OLI (Operational Land Imager) image acquired on July 21, 2019, and freely downloaded from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) website. The OLI sensor collected information in 11 bands. This paper used only the visible bands (2–4) and the NIR band (5) (Khan et al, 2005). A number of salinity indices, including SWIR-based indices (SI1–SI5), were calculated and assessed in addition to NDSI. However, the indices using SWIR bands did not enhance the prediction precision in comparison to NDSI; consequently, only NDSI was retained for full mapping and discussion. This period is characterised by high evapotranspiration rates and limited vegetation cover, which are favourable for detecting surface soil salinity. Vegetated and built-up areas were excluded using a supervised classification approach to focus the analysis on bare or sparsely vegetated soils. The salinity classes derived from NDSI represent spatially integrated surface conditions influenced by evaporation, irrigation practices, and salt accumulation at the soil surface, even though the majority of field EC measurements show non-saline to slightly saline conditions. The classification criteria were applied to the NDSI-derived EC estimates rather than directly to point-based field EC measurements, which explains the apparent distinction between laboratory EC statistics and mapped salinity classes. Figure 3 shows the methods used in outline form.

Tabela 2. Soil salinity indexes based on different band ratios of Landsat.

Table 2. Indeksi slanosti tal na podlagi različnih razmerij pasov Landsat.

Salinity Indexes	Spectral functions	References
Normalised Differential Salinity Index	$NDSI = \frac{R-NIR}{R+NIR}$	(Khan et al, 2005)
Brightness Index	$BI = \sqrt{R^2 + NIR^2}$	(Khan et al, 2005)
Salinity Index 1	$SI1 = \sqrt{B \times R}$	(Douaoui et al, 2006)
Salinity Index 2	$SI1 = \sqrt{G^2 + R^2 + NIR^2}$	(Douaoui et al, 2006)
Salinity Index 3	$SI3 = \frac{SWIR-1 \times SWIR-2 \times SWIR-2}{SWIR-1}$	(Bannari et al, 2008)
Salinity Index 4	$SI4 = \frac{R \times NIR}{G}$	(Abbas and Khan, 2007)
Salinity Index 5	$SI5 = \frac{G \times R}{B}$	(Bannari et al, 2008)

B, blue band; G, green band; R, red band; NIR, near-infrared band; SWIR 1 and SWIR 2, short-wave infrared 1 and 2 bands of the Landsat 8 image.

The Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) interpolation method was used to generate continuous spatial distribution maps of soil and climatic parameters across the study area (Eq. 2). Point-based values of soil electrical conductivity (EC), soil pH, soil organic matter (SOM), clay content, calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), and reference evapotranspiration (ET₂) obtained from weather stations were interpolated using this technique. IDW makes the assumption that a sampled point's influence diminishes with increasing distance, giving nearest observations more weight for estimating values in unsampled locations (Bhunja et al., 2018). The regional variability of soil characteristics associated with soil salinity was examined using the interpolated maps that were produced. ArcGIS 10.8 was used for all spatial analysis.

$$z(x_0) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{x_i}{h_{ij}^\beta}}{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{h_{ij}^\beta}} \quad (2)$$

Where Z (X₀) is the interpolation value; h_{ij} is the separation distance between the interpolation value and the measurement value; n is the number of sample points; x_i is the measurement value; β is the weight power (β=2).

The IDW interpolation method was chosen because it is simple to implement and suitable for large datasets with a relatively uniform distribution of sampling points. Soil parameters measured in the laboratory were interpolated to generate continuous spatial maps used in the analysis.

Statistical analysis of data

An investigation into the connections between soil salinity and other physicochemical parameters was carried out using advanced statistical methods by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The minimum, maximum, and mean values for each soil parameter were among the important descriptive statistics that could be determined thanks to this analysis. Additionally, the distribution characteristics of the data were evaluated by calculating skewness and kurtosis.

Results

Data of Evapotranspiration

The spatial distribution of daily reference evapotranspiration (ET_0) measured at 30 weather stations is shown in Figure 4. ET_0 values, which are measured in millimetres per day (mm day^{-1}) and range roughly from 4 to 8.5 mm

day^{-1} , show moderate spatial variability throughout the monitoring network. Overall, the majority of stations exhibit ET_0 values between 5 and 7 mm day^{-1} , suggesting that the study area's climate is rather uniform. However, a number of stations exhibit higher evapotranspiration rates of more than 8 mm day^{-1} , which could be linked to regional differences in meteorological elements like air temperature, solar radiation, wind speed, and atmospheric vapour pressure deficit. On the other hand, lower ET_0 values (less than 5 mm day^{-1}) at a small number of stations indicate the impact of more temperate weather. In order to accurately characterise evapotranspiration dynamics at the regional scale, multi-station observations are crucial. The observed spatial patterns of ET_0 highlight the combined effects of regional climate and local microclimatic variability.

Statistical analysis

Table 3 summarises the analytical results of the soil samples utilised for salinity mapping. To determine if the soil physicochemical characteristics were normal, histograms were

created (Fig. 5). Sand concentration varied from 26.8% to 90.6%, silt content from 3% to 25.3%, and clay content from 5.70% to 54.8%. The mean value of soil organic matter (SOM) was 1.61%, with values ranging from 0.24% to 4.8%. Soil pH readings varied from 7.0 to 9.1, while electrical conductivity (EC) ranged from 0.08 to 1.3 dS m⁻¹ with an average of 0.37 dS m⁻¹. Figure 6 shows the correlations between the various soil physicochemical properties.

In order to better understand the relationships between soil physicochemical characteristics and to identify the major variables that might be influencing the distribution of soil salinity in the research region, correlation analysis was carried out. It is possible to evaluate how soil texture, chemical characteristics, and electrical conductivity interact to affect salt transportation and accumulation in semi-arid conditions. In circumstances with heavy irrigation and high evapotranspiration, this type of analysis is essential for distinguishing between the direct and indirect effects of soil properties on salinity processes. Additionally, identifying important connections facilitates the selection of relevant factors for soil salinity modelling and improves the interpretation of geographical patterns displayed in the salinity maps produced from remote sensing data. This method offers a scientific foundation for sustainable soil and irrigation management techniques and advances a more thorough understanding of soil behaviour.

Spatial distribution of soil parameters

The primary soil physicochemical characteristics, such as soil SOM, pH, CaCO₃, electrical conductivity (EC), and clay content, are shown spatially throughout the study region in Figure 7. The spatial representation of these parameters was obtained by interpolating individual soil sample values using the Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW) approach, as described in the Materials and Methods section. The regional visualisation of the spatial variability of soil parameters was made possible by the use of IDW to create continuous surfaces while preserving the influence of pertinent data. Due to the discrete nature of sampling points and local variability in soil properties, individual point symbols are still visible in some places (e.g., Fig. 7c). These symbols were intentionally preserved to highlight original measurement locations and emphasise data reliability.

The region's soil fertility patterns were revealed by the soil organic matter (SOM) content, which varied from 0.24% to 4.8%. The majority of soils have moderate (1.5–3%) to

low (0.7–1.5%) SOM levels, according to the DIAEA (2008) interpretation standards (Fig. 7a). The pH values of the soil (Fig. 7b) range from 7.0 to 9.1, indicating primarily neutral to basic conditions. The total calcium carbonate content ranges from 0% to 8.8%. According to national standards (Badraoui et al., 2000), the majority of soils are categorised as non-calcareous (<5% CaCO₃), with only a few regions exhibiting slightly calcareous soils (5–30% CaCO₃) (Fig. 7c). Electrical conductivity values frequently remain below 4 dS m⁻¹ (Fig. 7d), indicating primarily non-saline soils, according to Brown et al. (1954). Hazelton and Murphy (2016) classified the majority of the study area as having a moderate clay concentration (25–40%) in terms of soil texture (Fig. 7e). These soils, which are primarily Vertisols, are known for their high-water retention capacity due to clay swelling, which enhances their capacity to retain salts in the upper soil layers under conditions of high evapotranspiration and irrigation. All things considered, these geographic distributions provide a comprehensive understanding of the soil heterogeneity in the Doukkala region and provide a strong basis for examining soil salinity patterns and the factors that affect them.

Relationship between experimental electrical conductivity and Penman-Monteith model outputs

The output from the Penman-Monteith equation, used to estimate soil evapotranspiration, was compared with the variation in electrical conductivity to assess the degree of correlation between these two parameters. Notably, a substantial correlation ($R^2 = 0.826$) was identified, as depicted in Fig. 8, between the EC in dS m⁻¹ and the Penman model values reflecting daily evaporation trends (mm. day⁻¹) [$Y (ET_0) = \text{Intercept} + B1 * X (EC)^{1.4}$]; $R^2 = 83\%$.

This correlation can help analyse how soil evaporation/evapotranspiration, influenced by the climatic context in the study area, impacts the variation in soil salinity. Essentially, it gauges how well the model output adapts to effectively manage soil irrigation and practical application.

The modelling performance was assessed using regression analysis between measured soil electrical conductivity (EC) and EC values predicted from spectral indices. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.90$) represents the relationship between NDSI values and measured EC and was used for evaluating the performance of the different salinity indices. A final calibrated regression model

Figure 4. Evapotranspiration (ETO mm.day⁻¹) values according to the use of Penman-Monteith equations and meteorological stations in the sampling period.

Slika 4. Vrednosti evapotranspiracije (ETO mm.dan⁻¹) v skladu z uporabo Penman-Monteithovih enačb in meteoroloških postaj v obdobju vzorčenja.

Figure 5. Normality histogram of soil parameters (n = 500).

Slika 5. Histogram normalnosti parametrov tal (n = 500).

Tabela 3. Statistics descriptive of soil parameters (n=500).

Table 3. Statistični opis parametrov tal (n=500).

Parameters	Min	Max	Mean	S. D	C V	Skewness	Kurtosis
Sand %	26.8	90.6	54.41	15.24	28.02	0.545	-0.666
Silt %	3	25.3	13.83	5.04	36.41	-0.126	-0.783
Clay %	5.7	54.8	32.06	11.45	35.71	-0.364	-0.703
EC dS.m ⁻¹	0.08	1.3	0.37	0.20	52.52	1.729	3.527
pH	7	9.1	8.10	0.37	4.60	-0.607	0.216
SOM %	0.24	4.8	1.61	0.64	39.52	1.202	2.539
CaCO ₃ %	0	8.8	1.01	1.67	165.32	2.43	5.754
ETO mm.day ⁻¹	4	8.5	6.18	1.17	18.93	0.142	-0.378

Figure 6. Pearson correlation between physicochemical parameters of the Doukkala soils.

Slika 6. Pearsonova korelacija med fizikalno-kemijskimi parametri tal v Doukkali.

Figure 7. Mapping of (a) SOM, (b) pH, (c) CaCO₃, (d) EC, and (e) Clay.

Slika 7. Kartiranje (a) SOM, (b) pH, (c) CaCO₃, (d) EC in (e) glin.

Figure 8. Correlation between ET0 and soil evapotranspiration.

Slika 8. Korelacija med ET0 in evapotranspiracijo tal.

was then developed for spatial prediction of soil salinity across the study area, yielding an additional coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.90$). Error metrics, such as the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which measure the difference between measured and predicted EC values, were used to further evaluate model accuracy.

Spatial variation of soil salinity using modelling

NDSI was found to be the most dependable indicator for mapping soil salinity out of all the tested spectral indices. The remote sensing-based soil salinity modelling approach was calibrated and validated using electrical conductivity (EC) data collected from soil sampling. These ground-based measurements were used to assess how well the tested spectral indices represented soil salinity conditions throughout the study area. The Normalised Difference Salinity Index (NDSI), which is computed as $NDSI = (R - NIR) / (R + NIR)$, was used to create a map of soil salinity. R and NIR

stand for the red and near-infrared bands of the Landsat 8 OLI image, respectively (Khan et al., 2005).

In the visible and near-infrared portions of the electromagnetic spectrum, this index takes advantage of the spectral difference between salt-affected soils and non-saline surfaces. Using agronomic salinity classification thresholds proposed by Brown et al. (1954), the resulting NDSI-derived salinity map (Fig. 9) was explained, classifying soils into five salinity classes ranging from non-saline ($<2 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$) to extremely saline ($>16 \text{ dS m}^{-1}$). This classification indicates that about 36% of the study area is unaffected by salinity.

Built-up areas were identified and excluded using supervised image classification to avoid misinterpretation of non-soil surfaces. Higher salinity levels were mainly observed in the northern, western, south-western, and central parts of the study area. The NDSI model showed the strongest statistical relationship with measured soil electrical conductivity among the tested indices, confirming its robustness for predicting and mapping the spatial distribution of soil salinity using multispectral satellite data.

Figure 9. Map of soil salinity based on NDSI in the Doukkala region.

Slika 9. Zemljevid slanosti tal na podlagi NDSI v regiji Doukkala.

Discussions

The study area, renowned for its agricultural productivity, particularly owes its fertility to the prevalence of loam and clay-loam soils. These soil types possess properties and fertility that make them suitable for significant crop yields. Coastal agricultural regions, like the study area, often feature soils with minimal permeability and excellent capillary capacity, such as loam and clay-loam (Ray et al, 2014). Previous studies (Feng et al., (2015); Sun et al., (2018); Tully et al., (2019); Taylor and Krüger (2019); Arulmathi and Porkodi (2020); de la Reguera and Tully (2021) and Guo and Liu (2023)) indicate that in these soils, more than 50% of the salt that infiltrates remain concentrated in the upper 1-meter layer even a year after contact with saline water. This ability to retain salt is attributed to the robust capillary action inherent in silt-loam and clay-loam soils. Indeed, among the critical soil parameters influencing salinity, clay content assumes significance due to its water absorption and swelling capacities. The water-retention

characteristics of clay offer a protective mechanism against the deleterious effects on crops and soil. However, challenges may emerge in the face of increased evaporation, particularly driven by elevated temperatures, leading to the evaporation of freshwater and subsequent salt accumulation in the soil. In contrast, sandy-loam soils, characterised by weaker capillarity due to higher permeability, exhibit less pronounced salt trapping. This suggests that silt-loam and clay-loam soils face challenges in recovering from saltwater irrigation. Consequently, the study area is deemed vulnerable to salinity, potentially impacting crop production. Given that 30% of the soils in the area are loam and clay-loam, combined with the prevailing climate conditions characterised by elevated temperatures leading to increased evaporation/evapotranspiration, the susceptibility to salinity poses a notable concern for crop cultivation.

In this research, soil salinity maps developed using the chosen computational model for NDSI revealed extensive areas with notable index values. The spatial distribution of this salinity classification varied across the studied

regions. Specifically, the study area exhibited heightened soil salinity, particularly in its northern, western, south-western, and central regions, depicted in blue on the map (Fig. 9) due to irrigation with saline water. The use of such saltwater for crop irrigation can result in salt accumulation in the topsoil. Conversely, arid regions (depicted in shades ranging from yellow to light blue) occur when saline water reaches the ground level, and high evaporation rates leave salt deposits on the soil surface (Al-Mahawili et al, 1983). Evaporation-driven water uptake is the reason for the elevated salt content in the superficial soil layer and upward capillary flow, following the stages of soil evaporation (Al Masmoudi et al, 2023). Therefore, these results imply that the utilisation of saltwater for irrigation, coupled with salt buildup at the soil surface and a high rate of evaporation, likely contributes significantly to the spatial disparities in soil salinity across these areas. Indeed, the pattern of occurrence of saline soils within the Doukkala area (Fig. 9) shows a moderate salinity content in parts of the study area, which is eventually related to the water irrigation quality (and/or climatic conditions, such as soil evaporation intensified by higher temperatures). To reduce the effect of soil salinity on crop yield production, several economic and scientific technologies should be adopted for sustainable agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability.

Variations in soil type and structure, the topography zone, inadequate drainage, and the quality of irrigation water could all contribute to differences in salinity levels across the study area. These factors are recognised as influencing the distribution of soil salinity across landscapes (Stavi et al, 2021). While irrigation water quality can pose challenges, these can be mitigated through effective management of irrigation. Additionally, it's worth noting that instruments for measuring and monitoring soil moisture content were not employed for irrigation purposes in any of the study area plots. Furthermore, many farmers may face financial constraints that prevent them from purchasing such instruments, and there may be a lack of extension services to promote their utilisation. As a result, improper irrigation practices, including excessive water applications and poor timing, can lead to varying degrees of salt accumulation in the soil profile, which is ultimately detrimental to crop production. This study demonstrates the effectiveness of utilising regression analysis alongside high-resolution remote sensing imagery to predict and map spatial variations in soil salinity across a region. The

new perspectives generated in this study may be helpful for farmers, scientists and engineers in the management of soil salinity problems in ecosystems. Furthermore, the low cost complexity of the proposed approach, and the satisfactory accuracy achieved by the presented approach make it an alternative to the traditional methods of soil salinity prediction and mapping. Although this study seeks to investigate the mapping and modelling of soil salinity's geographical fluctuation during a certain time period, future work should also address temporal variability in soil salinity in semi-arid and arid areas to recognise the evolving patterns of soil salinity over time. Previous studies conducted in the Doukkala region mainly focused on soil quality, erosion processes, or groundwater salinity. The spatial salinity patterns identified in this study are consistent with areas previously reported as vulnerable, which supports the validity of the proposed mapping approach and highlights its added value.

Soil salinity, being a phenomenon characterised by both spatial and temporal variations, necessitates further investigation into its temporal dynamics. Early identification of the salinity, as well as prediction and mapping of its severity and extent, allows decision-makers to take necessary decisions to protect date palm crops, agricultural lands, and natural ecosystems, especially in areas with severely saline soils. Furthermore, while this work yields promising results for predicting and mapping soil salinity using NDSI computing, there is room for future expansion to include hyperspectral imaging. Investigating how hyperspectral imagery can enhance the accuracy of spatial variation modelling and mapping in similar environments is a worthwhile endeavour. Numerous studies have highlighted the promising potential of hyperspectral imagery in assessing and mapping soil salinity (Allbed and Kumar, 2013; Hamzeh et al., 2016; Sytar et al., 2017). For example, with the aid of Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR) and Hyperion hyperspectral images, Gorji et al (2015) were able to predict and map soil salinity at a regional scale (>400,000 ha). Similarly, Goldshleger et al. (2013) and Fan et al. (2015) used the PLSR model to analyse the salt stress relationship of tomato plants, and soil spectral reflectance measured with a hyperspectral radiometer showed promise. They determined that hyperspectral radiometry is useful for measuring salinity in vegetative characterisation and estimating salt content. As a result, more research is needed to assess the capabilities of remote sensing data in mapping and predicting soil salinity under these conditions.

Conclusion

Agriculture stands as one of the primary activities for the population of the Doukkala region in Morocco. However, the progress of this activity is constrained by climatic conditions, the utilisation of saltwater in irrigation systems, and the physical degradation of agricultural soils. The climatic components impede crop development in the absence of suitable irrigation, leading to the accumulation of salts in the soil. This research revealed that electrical conductivity (EC) levels indicate varying degrees of salinity. Additionally, climate analysis within the region indicated a significant evapotranspiration rate (ET₀) ranging from 4 to 9 mm.day⁻¹. The model employed in the study demonstrated satisfactory results of the remote sensing approach in predicting soil salinity, achieving an R² value of 0.90. Furthermore, the generated map utilising NDSI illustrated that 36% of the total area showed no signs of salinity impact, 23% exhibited mild salinity, 24% indicated moderate soil salinity, and 17% displayed extreme levels of soil salinity. This strategic mapping of soil salinity in semi-arid and arid environments, combined with an advanced modelling approach utilising remote sensing data, serves as a crucial methodology for facilitating informed decision-making processes. Understanding the spatial variability of soil salinity is essential for sustainable agriculture in semi-arid regions. The approach proposed in this study provides a practical and cost-effective tool to support soil and irrigation management. Future research should focus on temporal monitoring and the integration of advanced modelling techniques to further improve soil salinity assessment.

Following the spatiotemporal dynamics of soil salinity is essential to comprehend the effects of precipitation, irrigation systems, and agricultural operations on its development. Consequently, agricultural researchers, utilising remote sensing and satellite imaging, can access essential intervention strategies to alleviate the enduring effects of soil salinisation on agricultural output. Since salt-tolerant plants can be useful for recovering saline soils in the region, it is advised that future research be done on growing halophilic plants in extremely saline areas.

Authorship contribution statement

Conceptualisation, Y.A., S.B., and A.J.; methodology, Y.A., S.B., and A.J.; validation, Y.A., S.B., and K.I.N.; formal analysis, Y.A.; investigation, Y.A. and S.B.; data curation, Y.A.; writing original draft preparation, Y.A. and S.B.; writing, review and editing, Y.A., S.B., K.I.N., A.J., M.M., M.L., and B. Rerhou; visualisation, K.I.N.; supervision, K.I.N. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

The authors declare that no funds, grants, or other support were received during the preparation of this manuscript.

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18717167>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Abbas, A., & Khan, S. (2007). Using remote sensing techniques for appraisal of irrigated soil salinity. *International Congress on Modelling and Simulation (MODSIM)*, 2632–2638. Modelling and Simulation Society of Australia and New Zealand.
- Ait Ayad, N., Ait Ayad, A., El Khalidi, K., Habib, A., & Charif, A. (2023). Remote sensing and meteorological indexes of drought using open short time-series data in Doukkala Region, Morocco. *Ecological Engineering & Environmental Technology*, 24.
- Al Masmoudi, Y., Bouslih, Y., Doumali, K., El Aissaoui, A., & Ibno Namr, K. (2021). Application of the random forest model to predict the plasticity state of Vertisols. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 22(2), 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/130878>
- Al Masmoudi, Y., El Aissaoui, A., & Ibno Namr, K. (2019). Evaluation of compaction in no-till Vertisol field using methods of cone index and pedotransfer function: Case of Moroccan semi-arid context. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology A*, 9, 141–150. <https://doi.org/10.17265/2161-6256/2019.03.001>
- Al Masmoudi, Y., Ibno Namr, K., El Youf, B., & El Aissaoui, A. (2023). Empirical model of Vertisol evaporation as a tool for management of soil practicability using portable lysimetric station under arid land context. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*, 25(2), 11–20.
- Allbed, A., & Kumar, L. (2013). Soil salinity mapping and monitoring in arid and semi-arid regions using remote sensing technology: A review. *Advances in Remote Sensing*, 2, 373–385. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ars.2013.24040>

- Allbed, A., Kumar, L., & Sinha, P. (2014). Mapping and modelling spatial variation in soil salinity in the Al Hassa Oasis based on remote sensing indicators and regression techniques. *Remote Sensing*, 6(2), 1137–1157. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs6021137>
- Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., Raes, D., & Smith, M. (1998). *Crop evapotranspiration: Guidelines for computing crop water requirements* (FAO Irrigation and Drainage Paper No. 56). FAO.
- Al-Mahawili, S. M. H., Baumgardner, M. F., Weismiller, R. A., & Melhorn, W. N. (1983). Satellite image interpretation and laboratory spectral reflectance measurements of saline and gypsiferous soils of West Baghdad, Iraq. LARS Technical Reports, Paper 104.
- Al-Maskri, A., Al-Kharusi, L., Al-Miqbali, H., & Khan, M. M. (2010). Effects of salinity stress on growth of lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*) under closed recycle nutrient film technique. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 12(3), 377–380.
- Amirul, A. M., Juraimi, A. S., Rafii, M. Y., Hamid, A. A., Uddin, M. K., Alam, M. Z., & Latif, M. A. (2014). Genetic improvement of purslane (*Portulaca oleracea* L.) and its future prospects. *Molecular Biology Reports*, 41, 7395–7411. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11033-014-3628-1>
- Aragüés, R., & Tanji, K. K. (2003). Water quality of irrigation return flows. In B. A. Stewart & T. A. Howell (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of water science* (pp. 502–506). Marcel Dekker.
- Arulmathi, C., & Porkodi, G. (2020). Characteristics of coastal saline soil and their management: A review. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 9(10), 1726–1734.
- Badraoui, M., Agbani, M., & Soudi, B. (2000). Evolution de la qualité des sols sous mise en valeur intensive au Maroc.
- Badraoui, M., Bouaziz, A., & Kabbassi, M. (1993). Contraintes physiques et potentialités du milieu sol dans les Doukkala. Projet: Développement et amélioration de la production céréalière en irrigué.
- Bai, L., Wang, C., Zang, S., Zhang, Y., Hao, Q., & Wu, Y. (2016). Remote sensing of soil alkalinity and salinity in the Wuyu'er Shuangyang River Basin, Northeast China. *Remote Sensing*, 8(2), 163. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs8020163>
- Bannari, A. (2019). Synergy between Sentinel MSI and Landsat OLI to support high temporal frequency for soil salinity monitoring in an arid landscape. In *Research developments in saline agriculture* (pp. 67–93). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-5832-6_3
- Bannari, A., Guedon, A. M., El-Harti, A., Cherkaoui, F. Z., & El-Ghmari, A. (2008). Characterization of slightly and moderately saline and sodic soils in irrigated agricultural land using simulated data of advanced land imaging (EO 1) sensor. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 39(19–20), 2795–2811. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103620802432717>
- Bel-Lahbib, S., Namr, K. I., El Hafyani, M., Al Masmoudi, Y., & Essahlaoui, A. (2022). Modelling and mapping of soil organic matter in Doukkala Plain, Moroccan semi arid region. *Ecological Engineering & Environmental Technology*, 23(5).
- Ben Dor, E., Chabrilat, S., Demattè, J. A. M., Taylor, G. R., Hill, J., Whiting, M. L., & Sommer, S. (2009). Using imaging spectroscopy to study soil properties. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 113, S38–S55.
- Ben Dor, E., Taylor, R. G., Hill, J., Demattè, J. A. M., Whiting, M. L., Chabrilat, S., & Sommer, S. (2008). Imaging spectrometry for soil applications. *Advances in Agronomy*, 97, 321–392. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(07\)00008-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(07)00008-9)
- Bhunja, G. S., Shit, P. K., & Maiti, R. (2018). Comparison of GIS based interpolation methods for spatial distribution of soil organic carbon. *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 17(2), 114–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssas.2016.02.001>
- Bounif, M., Rahimi, A., Boutafoust, R., & El Mjiri, I. (2023). Use of spatial remote sensing to study the temporal evolution of water retention of Al Massira Dam in Morocco. *Journal of Ecological Engineering*, 24(2). <https://doi.org/10.12911/22998993/156666>
- Brown, J. W., Hayward, H. E., Richards, A., Bernstein, L., Hatcher, J. T., Reeve, R. C., & Richards, L. A. (1954). *Diagnosis and improvement of saline and alkali soils* (USDA Agriculture Handbook No. 60). <https://doi.org/10.1093/aibsbulletin/4.3.14-a>
- Brunner, P. H. T. L., Li, H. T., Kinzelbach, W., & Li, W. P. (2007). Generating soil electrical conductivity maps at regional level by integrating measurements on the ground and remote sensing data. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 28(15), 3341–3361. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431160600928641>
- Curtis, P. S., & Lauchli, A. (1986). The role of leaf area development and photosynthetic capacity in determining growth of kenaf under moderate salt stress. *Functional Plant Biology*, 13(4), 553–565.
- De la Reguera, E., & Tully, K. L. (2021). Farming carbon: The link between saltwater intrusion and carbon storage in coastal agricultural fields. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 314, 107416.
- DIAEA/DRHA/SEEN. (2008). *Direction de l'irrigation et de l'aménagement de l'espace agricole, Service des expérimentations, des essais et de la normalisation*. Rabat.
- Douaoui, A., Hartani, T., & Lakehal, M. (2006). La salinisation dans la plaine du Bas Cheliff: Acquis et perspectives. In *Économies d'eau en systèmes irrigués au Maghreb, Deuxième atelier régional du projet SIRMA*.
- El Achheb, A., Mania, J., & Mudry, J. (2001). Processus de salinisation des eaux souterraines dans le bassin Sahel Doukkala (Maroc occidental). In *First International Conference on Saltwater Intrusion and Coastal Aquifers: Monitoring, Modeling and Management*, Essaouira, Morocco.
- El Bourhrami, B., Ibno Namr, K., Et-Tayeb, H., & Duraisamy, V. (2022). Application of Soil Quality Index to assess the status of soils submitted to intensive agriculture in the irrigated plain of Doukkala, Moroccan semiarid region. *Ecological Engineering and Environmental Technology*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.12912/27197050/145754>
- El Harti, A., Lhissou, R., Chokmani, K., Ouzemou, J. E., Hassouna, M., Bachaoui, E. M., & El Ghmari, A. (2016). Spatiotemporal monitoring of soil salinization in irrigated Tadla plain (Morocco) using satellite spectral indices. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 50, 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2016.03.008>

- Eldeiry, A. A., & Garcia, L. A. (2008). Detecting soil salinity in alfalfa fields using spatial modeling and remote sensing. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 72(1), 201–211. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2007.0013>
- Eldeiry, A. A., & Garcia, L. A. (2010). Comparison of ordinary kriging, regression kriging, and cokriging techniques to estimate soil salinity using Landsat images. *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering*, 136(6), 355–364. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)IR.1943-4774.0000208](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)IR.1943-4774.0000208)
- Eljebri, S., Mounir, M., Faroukh, A. T., Zouahri, A., & Tellal, R. (2019). Application of geostatistical methods for the spatial distribution of soils in the irrigated plain of Doukkala, Morocco. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 5(2), 669–687.
- Fan, X., Liu, Y., Tao, J., & Weng, Y. (2015). Soil salinity retrieval from advanced multispectral sensors with partial least squares regression. *Remote Sensing*, 7(1), 488–511. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs70100488>
- FAO. (2002). WFS: Focus on the issue.
- FAO. (2020). Salt affected Soils. <http://www.fao.org/soils portal/soil management/management of some problem soils/salt affected soils/more information on salt affected soils/en>
- Farifteh, J., Farshad, A., & George, R. J. (2006). Assessing salt affected soils using remote sensing, solute modelling, and geophysics. *Geoderma*, 130(3–4), 191–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2005.02.003>
- Feng, D., Zhang, J., Cao, C., Sun, J., Shao, L., Li, F., & Sun, C. (2015). Soil salt accumulation and crop yield under long term irrigation with saline water. *Journal of Irrigation and Drainage Engineering*, 141(12), 04015025.
- Goldshleger, N., Chudnovsky, A., & Ben Binyamin, R. (2013). Predicting salinity in tomato using soil reflectance spectra. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 34(17), 6079–6093. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2013.793859>
- Gorji, T., Tanik, A., & Sertel, E. (2015). Soil salinity prediction, monitoring, and mapping using modern technologies. *Procedia Earth and Planetary Science*, 15, 507–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeps.2015.08.062>
- Guo, K., & Liu, X. (2023). The successive infiltration of various saline waters accelerates infiltration processes and enhances salt leaching in a coastal saline soil. *Land Degradation & Development*, 34(16), 5083–5095.
- Hamzeh, S., Naseri, A. A., AlaviPanah, S. K., Bartholomeus, H., & Herold, M. (2016). Assessing the accuracy of hyperspectral and multispectral satellite imagery for categorical and quantitative mapping of salinity stress in sugarcane fields. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 52, 412–421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2016.06.024>
- Hazelton, P., & Murphy, B. (2016). *Interpreting soil test results: What do all the numbers mean?* CSIRO Publishing.
- Jamaa, H., El Achheb, A., & Ibno Namr, K. (2020). Spatial variation of groundwater quality and assessment of water table fluctuations in Plio Quaternary aquifer formations in Doukkala Plain, Morocco. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, 11, 100398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2020.100398>
- Jiapaer, G., Chen, X., & Bao, A. (2011). A comparison of methods for estimating fractional vegetation cover in arid regions. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 151(12), 1698–1710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2011.07.004>
- Kahime, K., Ben Salem, A., El Hidan, M. A., Messouli, M., & Chakhchar, A. (2018). Vulnerability and adaptation strategies to climate change on water resources and agriculture in Morocco: Focus on Marrakech Tansift Al Haouz. *International Journal of Agriculture and Environmental Research*, 4, 58–77.
- Khan, M. S. A., Chowdhury, J. A., Razzaque, M. A., Ali, M. Z., Paul, S. K., & Aziz, M. A. (2016). Dry matter production and seed yield of soybean as affected by post flowering salinity and water stress. *Bangladesh Agronomy Journal*, 19(2), 21–27.
- Khan, N. M., Rastokuev, V. V., Sato, Y., & Shiozawa, S. (2005). Assessment of hydrosaline land degradation using remote sensing indicators. *Agricultural Water Management*, 77(1–3), 96–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2004.09.038>
- Montanarella, L., Pennock, D. J., McKenzie, N., Badraoui, M., Chude, V., Baptista, I., Mamo, T., Yemefack, M., Singh Aulakh, M., Yagi, K., & Young Hong, S. (2016). World's soils are under threat. *Soil*, 2(1), 79–82.
- Moustakim, M., Benmansour, M., Nouira, A., Benkdad, A., & Damnati, B. (2022). Caesium 137 re sampling approach and excess lead 210 sediment dating to assess the impacts of climate change and agricultural practices on soil erosion and sedimentation in Northwest Morocco. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 81(10), 278.
- Moustakim, M., Benmansour, M., Zouagui, A., Nouira, A., Benkdad, A., & Damnati, B. (2019). Use of caesium 137 re sampling and excess lead 210 techniques to assess changes in soil redistribution rates within an agricultural field in Nakhla watershed. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 156, 158–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2019.04.017>
- Nanni, M. R., & Demattè, J. A. M. (2006). Spectral reflectance methodology in comparison to traditional soil analysis. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 70(2), 393–407. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2003.0285>
- Ors, S., & Suarez, D. L. (2017). Spinach biomass yield and physiological response to interactive salinity and water stress. *Agricultural Water Management*, 190, 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2017.05.003>
- Oumara, N. G. G. A., & El Youssfi, L. (2022). Salinization of soils and aquifers in Morocco and alternatives of response. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*, 16(1), 65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/envirosciproc2022016065>
- Patade, V. Y., Maya, K., & Zakwan, A. (2011). Seed priming mediated germination improvement and tolerance to subsequent exposure to cold and salt stress in Capsicum. *Research Journal of Seed Sciences*, 4, 125–136. <https://doi.org/10.3923/rjss.2011.125.136>
- Rahoui, M., Soudi, B., Badraoui, M., Marcoen, J. M., & Benzakour, M. (2000). Situation actuelle de la qualité des sols et des eaux dans le périmètre irrigué des Doukkala. *Séminaire: Intensification agricole et qualité des sols et des eaux*, Rabat, 2–3.
- Rao, R. R., & Kumar, K. S. (1991). Evolution of salinity field in the upper layers of the east central Arabian Sea and northern Bay of Bengal during summer monsoon experiments. *Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences – Earth and Planetary Sciences*, 100, 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02843485>

- Ray, P., Meena, B. L., & Nath, C. P. (2014). Management of coastal soils for improving soil quality and productivity. *Popular Kheti*, 2(1), 95–99.
- Rerhou, B., Mosseddaq, F., Naimi, M., Moughli, L., Ezzahiri, B., Bel Lahbib, S., Ibno Namr, K., & Mokri, F. (2023). Compost applications improve soil fertility, sugar beet performance, and decrease *Sclerotium rolfsii* survival under saline irrigation in a semi arid climate. *Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42729-023-01568-x>
- Robinson, M. F., Very, A. A., Sanders, D., & Mansfield, T. A. (1997). How can stomata contribute to salt tolerance? *Annals of Botany*, 80(4), 387–393. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/anbo.1996.0435>
- Shahbaz, M., & Ashraf, M. (2013). Improving salinity tolerance in cereals. *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 32, 237–249.
- Shrivastava, P., & Kumar, R. (2015). Soil salinity: A serious environmental issue and plant growth promoting bacteria as one of the tools for its alleviation. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 22(2), 123–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2014.12.001>
- Sidike, A., Zhao, S., & Wen, Y. (2014). Estimating soil salinity in Pingluo County of China using QuickBird data and soil reflectance spectra. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 26, 156–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2013.06.002>
- Srivastava, A., Tripathi, N. K., & Gokhale, K. V. G. K. (1997). Mapping groundwater salinity using IRS 1B LISS II data and GIS techniques. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 18(13), 2853–2862. <https://doi.org/10.1080/014311697217378>
- Stavi, I., Thevs, N., & Priori, S. (2021). Soil salinity and sodicity in drylands: A review of causes, effects, monitoring, and restoration measures. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 9, 712831. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.712831>
- Suárez, N., & Medina, E. (2005). Salinity effect on plant growth and leaf demography of the mangrove *Avicennia germinans* L. *Trees*, 19, 722–728.
- Sun, J., He, F., Zhang, Z., Shao, H., Pan, Y., Yang, R., & Zheng, M. (2018). Analysis of saline groundwater infiltration into two loam soils. *Land Degradation & Development*, 29(10), 3795–3802.
- Sytar, O., Brestic, M., Zivcak, M., Olsovska, K., Kovar, M., Shao, H., & He, X. (2017). Applying hyperspectral imaging to explore natural plant diversity towards improving salt stress tolerance. *Science of the Total Environment*, 578, 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.08.014>
- Tang, X., Mu, X., Shao, H., Wang, H., & Brestic, M. (2015). Global plant responding mechanisms to salt stress: Physiological and molecular levels and implications in biotechnology. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology*, 35(4), 425–437. <https://doi.org/10.3109/07388551.2014.889080>
- Taylor, M., & Krüger, N. (2019). Changes in salinity of a clay soil after a short term saltwater flood event. *Geoderma Regional*, 19, e00239.
- Tully, K. L., Weissman, D., Wyner, W. J., Miller, J., & Jordan, T. (2019). Soils in transition: Saltwater intrusion alters soil chemistry in agricultural fields. *Biogeochemistry*, 142(3), 339–356.
- Ug, M. V. M., & Douaik, A. (2008). Stochastic approaches for space time modelling and interpolation of soil salinity. In G. Metternicht & J. A. Zinck (Eds.), *Remote sensing of soil salinization: Impact on land management* (pp. 273–289). CRC Press.
- Walkley, A., & Black, I. A. (1934). An examination of the Degtjareff method for determining soil organic matter and a proposed modification of the chromic acid titration method. *Soil Science*, 37(1), 29–38. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/00010694-193401000-00003>
- Yadav, S., Modi, P., Dave, A., Vijapura, A., Patel, D., & Patel, M. (2020). Effect of abiotic stress on crops. In *Sustainable Crop Production*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.88434>
- Yamaguchi, T., & Blumwald, E. (2005). Developing salt tolerant crop plants: Challenges and opportunities. *Trends in Plant Science*, 10(12), 615–620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2005.10.002>